

KNOWKALINGA: A KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF CULTURAL HERITAGE RESEARCH CENTER (CHRC)

Joy Lyn B. Jimenez, LPT., Mike Anthony D. Gragasin

*College of Information Technology and Computer Science, University of the Cordilleras,
Baguio City, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

The research paper 'KnowKalinga: A Knowledge Management System for Cultural Heritage Research Center (CHRC)' describes the design, development, and deployment of an online system that is dedicated to the preservation and promotion of Kalinga Heritage Culture. The paper addresses the challenges CHRC has faced during its attempts to achieve its vision and mission. The developed innovative online system is based on the WordPress platform and is client-centered. The clients include Kalinga Culture students, educators, researchers, and enthusiasts, as the platform serves as a centralized database and a sharing platform. The defined components consist of a cultural heritage research database, a learning center, interactive components, and collaboration tools that support client-to-client interaction. The paper proves the importance of the KnowKalinga system as a cultural awareness and preservation tool that stimulates collaboration and contributes to sustainable preservation. The paper as innovation describes significant meaning for the knowledge management and technology-enabled cultural preservation fields.

Keywords: *KnowKalinga, Cultural Preservation, CHRC, Digitalization, Indigenous Culture*

INTRODUCTION

“A people without knowledge of their history, origin, and culture is like a tree without roots” is a famous word from Marcus Garvey, inspires every one of us to have an important goal to preserve our cultural heritage to protect our unique traditions, practices and cultural knowledge for the future generations. According to Loriene Roy (2015) preservation of our cultural heritage is concerned with safeguarding the tangible representations of the culture including cultural clothing, pottery, and beadworks, as well as the non-tangible aspects of our culture such as language, oral stories, customs, and beliefs. We learn and understand our culture more from the stories and songs that our elders and forefathers shared, McQueen, J. (2019), thus, technology integration can help share and preserve this slowly vanishing cultural heritage, especially in this age of digital innovation. According to Hershey, R. (2010), many people believe that the Internet can be a tool to protect, maintain, and promote cultural diversity. As emphasized by Shiri, A. et al. (2021) in their study that across the world, Indigenous communities are increasingly interested in exploring digital technologies for different uses ranging from education, social engagement, cultural heritage preservation, and even initiatives aimed at stimulating distressingly grim prospects for language revitalization. Modern technology has the power to take digital storytelling possibilities to the next level, and the above is just one example of how it can help contemporary Indigenous groups. However as stated by Mdhluli, T.D., et al. (2021), the use of technology especially digitalization in preserving Indigenous knowledge (IK) has some challenges such as fears of issues related to copyright, intellectual property rights, and exploitation by external entities. There are also concerns about misinformation or misrepresentation of Indigenous knowledge which can potentially harm the authenticity and integrity of the Indigenous information. Regardless of the challenges and concerns digital libraries provide a solution, however, proper caution has to be exercised to avoid the pitfalls of ethics thereby guaranteeing successful preservation, management, and sharing of Indigenous Knowledge to future generations. Furthermore, cultural and natural heritages are referred to as treasures, and they are unique tourist destinations for every country. But turning this legacy - and this liability - into sustainable tourism development that will also safeguard the cultural heritage value for the future is much less straightforward, Pandey, R. et al. (2020). Defined and rooted in the preservation of cultural heritage, sustainable development means that we meet the needs of the current society without hindering the capacity of future generations to develop. Both community participation and public education, along with technological development are important in ensuring the durable preservation and display of cultural heritage in the light of environmental and societal change, Hoang, K. (2021).

As reported by Liew, C. et al (2021) With technology changing and how back in the day you necessarily be physically present in the place to understand better the Indigenous culture of a place but now that it's all been documented and moved to an online platform where it can be stored and accessed at all times, that's the part that makes these

digitalized collections most useful and the youth of today which very much inhabits this technological and digital world better resonates with digitalized information. For example, the Lha'hutit'en Digital Storytelling by Freeman, S. (2020) workshops with Elders and youth are just one example of bringing together people to restore what Indigenous elders hold collectively, ie: knowledge and insight into the culture. Sharing and learning from each other can create the long-term Intergenerational relationships that are so important in safeguarding cultural heritage. Co-convened by community and academic partners, this Learning Centre case illustrates the implications of intergenerational memory for protecting Indigenous legacies in the digital age. Hence, this research paper will explore the development and implementation of "KnowKalinga.com" a collaborative online system devised to promote cultural engagement.

Kalinga is one of the provinces with a rich cultural legacy that includes many traditions, rituals, arts folklore, and indigenous practices. However, as time goes on, it becomes evident that it runs the risk of losing this priceless cultural legacy. Oral traditions and cultures of our ancestors are at risk of being lost, so mobilizing the power of technology and putting it in the hands of young people is one way that policymakers are taking into consideration. Hence, efforts are being made by different organizations to promote and preserve cultural heritage, because of that, the integration of cultural heritage into students' curriculum is one of the measures that CHED-CAR has done. However, the availability of learning resources and materials is limited and some are subject to information checking. As a creative response to this issue, "KnowKalinga" is being developed, fusing technology and teamwork to provide a dynamic platform for promoting cultural preservation, education, and engagement among teachers, students, researchers, and Indigenous culture enthusiasts. Based on Suaib, N. et al. (2020) study found from the literature, most of the preservation efforts (including usage of computer graphics and media) reported were mostly centered around tangible cultural heritage. Since computer graphics and media technology has so much to offer, there are endless possibilities for cultural preservation efforts digitally both for tangible and intangible cultural heritage preservation.

Specifically, the overall goal of KnowKalinga is to develop an all-inclusive digital ecosystem for CHRC that integrates all the stakeholders in the endeavor to salvage and disseminate the cultural heritage of Kalinga province. KnowKalinga is envisaged as a single-stop shop where relevant information can be accessed regarding the rich cultural heritage of the people of Kalinga. The platform provides learning materials to educational institutions that can be embedded in the respective syllabi as content to be used in teaching to ensure it is a perfect source of information for all the activities that take place in schools. The system also avails relevant information to students to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the content while ensuring they have the right information to access the learning model that promotes an in-depth understanding of the rich culture and tradition of the natives. Apart from school use, the platform also provides researchers with a prestigious forum to disseminate and publish their findings in the area

without fears of contradiction since it is supervised by CHRC. They can also access other academic materials on the platform to support their research projects. Tourists and cultural enthusiasts also access the platform to gain insight into the culture, tradition, and practice of the Kalinga people and beyond to achieve a complete understanding of the rich culture of the province as the information also helps boost safe tourism. The internet age when one needs to browse many websites to obtain information that may be inaccurate and lack authenticity is gone; with the supervision of CHRC, the system acts as a source of the truth and trusted information about Kalinga Province. Moreover, the Kalinga Province is divided into several tribes and sub-tribes all with unique practices and traditions within their culture. Therefore, the information-sharing capability of the platform where the users can contribute their experiences with each cultural practice to support each tale in the platform is the rock-bottom focus of the platform. The sharing triggers debates, generates useful information, and elicits sober views that may be used for research projects. The platform design promotes usage that allows users to upload their views about Kalinga culture and their research results.

Research Questions

The research paper entitled, "KnowKalinga: A Knowledge Management System for CHRC", primarily addresses the design, implementation, and evaluation of KnowKalinga as a knowledge management system for CHRC. The focus includes its development, implementation, and evaluation as a comprehensive solution for protecting, promoting, and sharing Kalinga's cultural heritage through learning materials, consolidated research repositories, user engagement features for cultural mapping as well as local crafter and artist promotion; it also investigates its usability through System Usability Scale (SUS), to measure the system's user-friendliness. The system celebrates the diversity of viewpoints and experiences, enhancing collective understanding of Kalinga's cultural heritage and its development and implementation is better discussed by answering the following research questions:

1. What are the challenges the Cultural Heritage Research Center of SLCB experienced in realizing its mission of preserving and promoting Kalinga's cultural heritage?
2. What innovative technological solutions will help support the Cultural Heritage Research Center of SLCB in preserving, promoting, and sharing Kalinga's cultural heritage in this digital age?
3. What are the features of the system that can be integrated to answer the challenges the Cultural Heritage Research Center of SLCB experienced?
4. What is the level of user acceptability of the developed system, what challenges do users encounter, and recommendations for the proposed IT solutions improvement and sustainability?

However, it is also essential to recognize certain limitations within this research. The research's primary focus is the design and creation of KnowKalinga for CHRC

exclusively and excludes actual content generation such as research papers, learning materials, and cultural mapping. The research also focused on the promotion of local arts and crafts of the Kalinga people but online shops are not included in the system. Nevertheless, the research provides invaluable insights into the hands-on establishment of a knowledge management system dedicated to cultural heritage preservation.

METHODOLOGY

Agile scrum methodology is the combination of the agile philosophy and the scrum framework. Agile means “incremental, allowing teams to develop projects in small increments. Scrum is one of the many types of agile methodology, known for breaking projects down into sizable chunks called “sprints.” Agile scrum methodology is good for businesses that must finish specific projects quickly [5]. The Scrum methodology helps the researchers emphasize iterative development, collaboration, and flexibility for designing and implementing the proposed IT solution, hence the steps that the researchers undertake are listed below:

- **Product Backlog Creation:** Researchers collaborated with stakeholders to generate a list of all features, functionalities and requirements necessary for the KnowKalinga system to be complete. This list, known as Product Backlog serves as a comprehensive outline of its goals.
- **Sprint Planning:** Researchers in this phase selected items from their product backlog that they plan to work on during an upcoming sprint (a time-boxed development cycle, usually lasting 2-4 weeks). As part of this planning session, the team decided on the scope, goals, and tasks that must be achieved within that sprint.
- **Sprint Execution:** Researchers began implementing tasks specified in their sprint plan. Daily stand-up meetings were held to review progress and challenges, and plan the next steps. Working as part of a collaborative environment, various roles such as frontend development, content gathering, testing, and design were filled by researchers.
- **Daily Stand-Up Meetings:** Researchers convened briefly every week for short updates. They reviewed what had been accomplished over the previous week, discussed any plans they had for that particular week, and whether any impediments or challenges required addressing.
- **Sprint Review:** After each sprint, researchers presented their work to stakeholders - including CHRC Office staff - for feedback and validation of any features created during it. The CHRC Head, Sir. Danao evaluated the versions of the project and gave constructive criticism and recommendations for the enhancement of the project. Based on the feedback received, adjustments were then implemented

based on user comments. The project conducted a total of three sprints before the product was accepted by the CHRC Head and recommended for implementation.

- Sprint Retrospective: Following each sprint review meeting, the researchers held a retrospective meeting to analyze what went well and where improvements can be made in their development process. This enabled them to continually optimize and enhance their work methods.

In all of these steps, the researchers exercised collaboration, adaptability, and responsiveness. They had been communicating regularly with their stakeholders and soliciting their input at all times to approve that KnowKalinga was wholly created out of their specifications and anticipation. Agile Scrum gave the researchers the power to immediately and intelligently respond, make adjustments, mitigate any possible challenges, and develop a system that shall adequately educate others about the promotion and conservation of Kalinga. The tools chosen by KnowKalinga researchers to build the system are a selected set that gives them more control and the ability to customize. Consequently, their preferred Relational Database Management System is MariaDB. This RDBMS is the repository of all the user accounts, learning materials, and everyone's data, the research and the findings, the interactions on the forums, and other website-related data – ensures the integrity of the data and the data organization as well as a swift and efficient retrieval. They also selected the web Host service, Hostinger, which has been very secure and reliable for hosting the infrastructure of the KnowKalinga system. The robust system of deployment, scaling, and performance has left the researchers with only one thing to focus on, the experience to provide to the users. This is an important choice the researchers made when developing the Knowledge Management System based on the fact that the system's security and reliability in terms of content management depended on the platform. The choice was in two folds; utility which is more secure given its popularity and implications, and simplicity for easy utilization by information content creators and managers at CHRC.

RESULTS

To evaluate usability, the researchers employed the System Usability Scale (SUS), a validated tool containing 10 questions with response options ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." Table 1 below displays this data that offers insight into user-friendliness and the effectiveness of systems.

KnowKalinga SUS Survey Results							
Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Odd Sum	Even Sum
1	13	8	0	0	0	21	8
2	0	7	7	11	5	14	16
3	12	7	1	2	1	21	8
4	0	2	3	12	2	5	14
5	10	7	1	0	0	18	8
6	0	7	4	11	2	11	13
7	10	7	1	0	0	18	8
8	0	2	3	10	3	5	13
9	10	7	2	0	0	19	9
10	0	6	3	4	9	9	13

Table 1. SUS survey results

The SUS survey was conducted by asking a number of respondents about how they feel when using the system. Each participant should choose between “Strongly Disagree” and “Strongly Agree” at 10 statements/questions. The researcher counted how many are the answers for the odd-numbered question and how many for evens. For example, the results show that the score is 49 from odd ones and 72 from even, on the score sheet the odd score will be subtracted from the even score ($72-49= 23$) and that would be 23. The total SUS Score was found by multiplying each persons' score by 2.5 and placing it all together. In this case, the result was about 57.5. The explanation value of these results was implemented according to guidelines and lies between “Good” and “Excellent”. It means that the majority of people would easily use the system, but opportunities for improvement still exists. Generally, the survey explains that people like to use the KnowKalinga: Knowledge Management System. At the same time, it allows the researchers to get some valuable feedback from target audiences to improve the current system and fix all the issues respondents could have experienced during their interaction with this system.

DISCUSSION

This section provides the main findings of the research which address the impediments faced by the Cultural Heritage Research Center in preserving and promoting Kalinga’s heritage. Moreover, this section will also provide the technology innovation solutions in the KnowKalinga: Knowledge Management system implemented to improve the identified features and their usability rating for recommendations to improve and sustain the system.

The following research determined some of the problems that the SLCB's Cultural Heritage Research Center had, making missions to protect as well as foster the cultural heritage of Kalinga difficult. Among other issues was the manual consolidation of researchers' works, which made the management of knowledge inefficient and slow. Secondly, the shared access to cultural resources was the biggest problem that CHRC faced. Since CHRC was not able to share its collection of the overall research, and educational materials on the diverse cultural aspects of Kalinga culture such as traditional arts, rituals, local cultures, and locale knowledge, the institution was not able to be a Kalinga cultural heritage repository and hub; lastly, both teachers and student were facing difficulty in finding correct and relevant cultural heritage information on the website. Hence, the available information contained inaccurate and incomplete information from unreliable websites.

In addition to this, the CHRC faced challenges in engaging all stakeholders including putting their ideas together in an inclusive manner. If there was a provided platform to facilitate knowledge sharing and cultural preservation amongst students, educators, researchers, indigenous culture enthusiasts, tourists, and a community; collaboration research would be highly effective and enhance learning from the activities.

To address the challenges presented by CHRC, this study proposed innovative technological solutions that promote the preservation, promotion, and sharing of Kalinga's cultural heritage in digital form. The researchers proposed a Knowledge Management System for CHRC "KnowKalinga", which is an online system that serves as the Kalinga Cultural Heritage research and knowledge repository utilizing WordPress as a Content Management Tool which includes the following architecture and features:

Figure 2. System Architectural Diagram

KnowKalinga system This reengineered system, based on an enhanced client-server architecture and a responsive and adaptable web application interface that can be accessed across laptops, desktops, smartphones, and tablets via any web browser, is easily accessible online for enhanced user convenience. The Cultural Heritage Research Center is at the heart of this system, acting as its central cloud infrastructure provider and administrator. CHRC plays an essential role in reviewing and approving research, learning materials, and content submitted and/or approved by stakeholders ensuring authenticity and quality before uploading to the system.

The CHRC Office retains its role as server manager, rationalizing the tracking of official records and the reviewing of data and content flow while also managing the advertisements local artisans upload onto the system. The client-server architecture promoted a smooth user experience in terms of viewing and providing feedback to other users and maintaining high-quality content through the CHRC Office's extensive checks

Screenshot 1 & 2. Administrator Dashboard and Post Management Board

The Admin Dashboard is the central control hub, an interface that empowers the admin to create, curate, and manage content for the cultural heritage project in Kalinga. This is an intuitive interface to make the work of uploading materials faster and easier, enabling them to readily access relevant resources about Kalinga's heritage.

Screenshot 3. Administrator Comment Management Board

Further, Administrators play a vital role in maintaining Kalinga's cultural heritage while providing users with genuine insights and authentic feedback in the Admin Dashboard. By fact-checking and filtering feedback and comments submitted by users,

administrators ensure accurate and reliable information dissemination throughout the system.

Screenshot 4. System Visitors Board

Meanwhile, Visitors Dashboard provides a vibrant slide show picture illustrating landscapes of different parts of Kalinga Province and exposes the interests and/or attractions of the 8 municipalities composing Kalinga on the lower portion of its page. In its screen front view, this lay-out welcomes visitors and informs them about the cultural richness and historical landmarks of the vibrant province.

The Learning Materials Dashboard is an extensive library of educational resources on Kalinga Cultural Heritage. To make these learning materials easily available to students, educators, researchers, and enthusiasts each item has been thoroughly cataloged with titles and authors. Users can engage with a range of subjects to deepen their understanding of Kalinga's vibrant legacy from traditional arts, rituals, indigenous practices, and more.

Screenshot 5. Learning Materials Dashboard

Screenshot 6. Research Papers Dashboards

The preceding page contains a comprehensive list of research compiled by the CHRC office. It reveals much information about the valuable cultural heritage of Kalinga. As a repository and sharing platform, the research papers not only keep much-needed records but also shows various perspectives: this way, the system creates an environment wherein other researchers might be inspired or learn from one another and be able to write a more comprehensive work on the same topic in the future. Hence it serves its primary purpose for which the CHRC office intended, and it also fosters exchange and innovation of knowledge within academic communities.

Screenshot 7. Tourist Spots Dashboard

The last section is a complete list of every tourist destination found in Kalinga Province. When the user clicks on a particular destination, he or she is connected to a more accessible summary explaining the importance, history, fascinating stories, and sub-specifics such as drop-off points, tour guide costs if one wants to use one, and more. Furthermore, the researchers have placed coordinates that can be clicked, and locations are quickly accessible by any user as it can quickly use Google Maps for each direction that goes directly to the tourist's point they are interested.

An error occurred. The user whose profile picture was used as a placeholder for a user that developed the error has
removed the "Display Name" field. The user's profile picture is now blank. The user's profile picture is now blank.

Latest Comments

Leave a Reply

Your email address will not be published. Required fields are marked *

Comment *

Name *

Email *

Website

Save my name, email, and website in this browser for the next time I comment.

Screenshot 8. Visitors Comment Section

Being a land of different tribes and sub-tribes, it is clear that different interpretations of traditions practices and customs exist. Through the Visitors Comment Section provided in each uploaded content in the system, site users are enabled to post meaningful comments, encouraging users to share their thoughts, ideas, and opinions to create an ongoing debate around the cultural heritage of Kalinga. This feature becomes particularly vital as a virtual space for knowledge-sharing among community members; by providing this forum for the collaborative exchange of insights among them all it fosters a greater appreciation of Kalinga's rich cultural tapestry.

Conclusions

The research goal is to create a KnowKalinga Knowledge Management System as an attempt to protect, promote, and share Kalinga Cultural Heritage. The main challenge of Cultural Heritage Research Center (CHRC) is not having a centralized repository and sharing platform for the consolidation of the data and research they have accumulated in the office. Hence, to answer this the researchers develop a system that is integrated with features such as a centralized repository of well-curated learning materials and research of Cultural Heritage Research Center (CHRC), interactive culture-mapping for its users, and promotion of local artists and crafts. The use of WordPress in the development of the system has allowed easy editing and customization of the content and its client-server design assured smooth interactions and distribution of materials. Testing using the System Usability Scale user study reveals that the system excelled in its usability where services can be easily accessed and used by the various segments of users.

The KnowKalinga Knowledge Management System not only fills the knowledge gap for educators, students, researchers, tourists, and culture enthusiasts but also helps CHRC to achieve its mission of recognizing the cultural heritage of Kalinga and passing it on to the next generations. Positive responses to the survey suggest that this system has the potential to be used for educational purposes, appreciating cultures, and collaborations. KnowKalinga is an example of integrating technology and culture by assisting the understanding and promotion of Kalinga's diverse history for the next generations and users' participation and content improvement. It is expected to be beneficial through the participation of users and the improvement of content.

Recommendations

Considering the findings of the study, the researchers proposed the following recommendations: a.) Preserve the cultural artifacts, documents, and oral tradition in a digital format using modern technology. This will allow the artifacts to be properly archived and accessed long-term by both the current and the future generations. b.) Future researchers need to conduct more extensive and inclusive testing of the proposed method. Having a higher confidence level in the results will ensure that the usability of the proposed method tested is accurate. c.) Future research must focus on the better protection of the data records and optimize the process.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

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